

STREAMLINING ACADEMIC RESEARCH OPERATIONS: A BUSINESS PROCESS REENGINEERING CASE STUDY OF HOLY CROSS COLLEGE, STA. ROSA, N.E., INC.

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates and reengineers the undergraduate research process at Holy Cross College, Sta. Rosa, N.E., aiming to bridge the gap between ideal and current states. Using a mixed-method approach, it assesses student perceptions across multiple research stages and identifies challenges such as time constraints, collaboration dynamics, and resource limitations. Findings highlight strong institutional support in stages like Research Final Defense but reveal opportunities for improvement in communication channels, preparation time, and publication support. Recommendations focus on enhancing these areas to optimize the research process for undergraduate researchers. Future studies could explore longitudinal impacts and technological solutions to further enhance research environments.

Keywords: *Undergraduate research, academic management, process reengineering, institutional support, student perceptions*

INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education, the optimization of academic research operations has become a critical priority for institutions striving to maintain academic excellence and enhance the research experience for their students (Wang, 2021). Efficient research operations directly impact the quality of research output and

the academic development of students (Rhaiem, 2017). Not only do streamlined processes save time and resources, but they also enhance the overall research experience, leading to higher satisfaction among researchers and better (Szromek & Wolniak, 2020). Thus, optimizing these processes is essential for academic institutions aiming to foster a robust research culture and maintain competitive standards.

However, research operations in academic settings often face numerous challenges. Bureaucratic delays, with multiple layers of approval and review, significantly slow down the research process (Thompson & France, 2010). Redundant processes, characterized by overlapping responsibilities and unnecessary steps, create inefficiencies that further complicate the workflow (Miranda & Lerner, 2018). Additionally, poor communication and coordination among faculty, researchers, and administrative staff can lead to misunderstandings and errors, exacerbating delays (Albalawi & Nadeem, 2020). Many institutions also rely on paper-based systems or outdated digital tools, which hampers efficiency and productivity (Santos & Jocson, 2021).

Business Process Reengineering (BPR) offers a strategic approach to addressing these challenges by fundamentally rethinking and redesigning processes to achieve significant performance improvements (Zaini & Saad, 2019). BPR focuses on streamlining operations, eliminating redundancies, and leveraging technology to enhance efficiency and effectiveness.

Numerous case studies highlight the successful application of BPR in academic settings. For example, Hasouneh et al. (2024) reported on the reengineering of administrative processes in universities, resulting in faster processing times and improved service quality. Similarly, Mostafa et al. (2022) discussed the transformation of academic advising and registration processes through BPR, leading to enhanced student satisfaction and reduced administrative workload. In the context of research operations, BPR can streamline approval processes by reducing the number of approval stages and introducing parallel processing, thereby shortening timelines (Popoola et al., 2024). Improved coordination and communication can be achieved by implementing collaborative tools and platforms that enhance communication among researchers, faculty, and administrative staff. Additionally, adopting digital tools for document management, data collection, and analysis can increase efficiency and accuracy.

Roberts (1994) as cited in Bhaskar (2018) introduces a structured BPR framework that commences with a gap analysis and culminates in a pathway towards continuous improvement (see Figure 4). his framework starts by identifying three critical questions: (1) defining how processes ideally should function, (2) assessing their current state, and (3) determining strategies to bridge the gap between these two states. By undertaking a comprehensive reassessment of workflows and integrating innovative solutions, institutions can streamline approval processes, introduce parallel processing to expedite timelines and enhance coordination through collaborative digital platforms.

Holy Cross College, Sta. Rosa, N.E., recognizes the importance of streamlining its research processes to foster an environment that supports efficient and effective

scholarly activities. The research process is structured into several key stages, as outlined in the College's research manual. These stages include the preparation and submission of research preliminaries, the development and defense of a research proposal, the ethical review, the completion of a full research paper, the final defense, and ultimately, the publication and presentation of the research output. Each of these stages involves specific procedures and requirements, designed to guide undergraduate researchers through a systematic and rigorous research journey.

Despite the well-defined framework, there may be gaps that can serve as opportunities to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the research process. To address these gaps, this study adopts the Business Process Reengineering (BPR) framework with a gap analysis. This structured approach begins with defining the ideal state of research processes, which aligns with the detailed procedures outlined in Holy Cross College's research manual. The study then evaluates the current status of these processes through a thorough assessment of existing operations across various research stages.

The core objective of this study is to evaluate the overall research process and identify the challenges and potential improvements that arise from the gap between the ideal and current states of research operations at Holy Cross College. This will be achieved by formulating strategic recommendations for reengineering the current process based on the findings and insights derived from the assessment. These recommendations will focus on streamlining workflows, reducing bureaucratic hurdles, enhancing communication channels, and leveraging technological advancements to optimize the research process for undergraduate researchers.

By applying the BPR framework with gap analysis, Holy Cross College aims to set a precedent for other academic institutions seeking to optimize their research operations. The findings and recommendations presented in this paper will not only contribute to the enhancement of the College's research processes but also provide valuable insights for the broader academic community on the application of Business Process Reengineering in higher education research administration.

Research Questions

This study aims to bridge the gap between the ideal and current states of the undergraduate research process at Holy Cross College and seeks to answer the following research problems:

1. How may the evaluation of the undergraduate research process be described?
2. What are the primary challenges encountered by respondents in the undergraduate research process?
3. What suggestions for improvement were provided by respondents regarding the undergraduate research process?
4. What reengineered processes should be integrated with the current process based on the identified challenges and suggestions for improvement?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-method approach to thoroughly investigate and reengineer the academic research operations at Holy Cross College, Sta. Rosa, N.E. The research design was descriptive, integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies to comprehensively understand the current research processes and identify areas for enhancement (Matović & Ovesni, 2023).

The sample for this study was selected using purposive sampling, targeting 50 undergraduate researchers who were engaged in the current research process at Holy Cross College, Sta. Rosa, N.E., Inc. This sampling method ensured that participants possessed direct experience and insights relevant to the research objectives, spanning stages from research preliminaries to final defense and publication (Pacho, 2015).

Data collection utilized two main approaches: a structured survey employing a Likert scale to assess participants' perceptions of various research stages, focusing on aspects such as clarity of guidelines, adequacy of support mechanisms, and overall satisfaction. Additionally, open-ended questions were employed to solicit qualitative feedback on challenges encountered by researchers and opportunities for process improvement.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics—including means—to provide a quantitative overview of participant perceptions. Qualitative data underwent thematic analysis to uncover underlying patterns and themes within participants' narratives on the challenges encountered and their suggestions for improvement in the overall process, offering deeper insights into the dynamics of the research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The objective of this study was to bridge the gap between the ideal and current states of research operations at Holy Cross College. By assessing the current processes and identifying key areas for improvement, the study aimed to formulate strategic recommendations for streamlining workflows, reducing bureaucratic hurdles, enhancing communication channels, and leveraging technological advancements to optimize the research journey for undergraduate researchers.

Evaluation of the Undergraduate Research Process

Table 1. Evaluation of the Undergraduate Research Process

Stage	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. Research Preliminaries	3.65	SA
2. Research Proposal	3.66	SA
3. Research Proposal Defense	3.69	SA

4. Approval of Request Letters	3.53	SA
5. Full Research Paper	3.67	SA
6. Research Final Defense	3.80	SA
7. Research Output	3.76	SA
8. Research Publication and Presentation	3.48	SA
Overall	3.65	SA

The evaluation of the undergraduate research process at Holy Cross College, as summarized in Table 1, reveals generally positive perceptions across various stages, reflecting strong agreement (SA) with the effectiveness of support and processes. Key preparation stages such as Research Preliminaries (3.65), Research Proposal (3.66), and Full Research Paper (3.67) received high ratings, indicating satisfaction with the clarity of instructions, adequacy of support from advisory panels, and the constructive nature of feedback received.

Notably, the Research Final Defense stage garnered the highest overall rating of 3.80, emphasizing the structured and beneficial nature of this critical phase in validating research efforts. This high rating suggests that students felt well-prepared and supported during this crucial stage, which is pivotal in the academic validation of their research work. The Research Output stage also received a commendable rating of 3.76, indicating that the end products of the research process were perceived positively by the participants.

However, the Research Publication and Presentation stage received the lowest mean score of 3.48, implying the presence of challenges in the publication and presentation of the completed research output. This lower rating suggests that while students felt confident in their research process and final defense, they encountered difficulties in the final stages of disseminating their research findings. These challenges could stem from a lack of sufficient guidance or support in navigating the publication process, unfamiliarity with presentation formats, or difficulties in accessing appropriate platforms for dissemination.

Despite these challenges, the overall rating of 3.65 indicates a generally satisfactory experience for the undergraduate researchers. The positive feedback on most stages of the research process underscores the strengths of the current system, particularly in its early and middle stages, where clear guidelines and supportive advisory mechanisms seem to be effectively in place.

Overall, while Holy Cross College excels in many aspects of its undergraduate research process, there remains room for improvement. The challenges and suggestions for improvement based on the respondents' feedback were identified.

Challenges in the Undergraduate Research Process

Following the evaluation of the undergraduate research process, respondents identified significant challenges encountered across various stages. These challenges were consolidated into emerging themes, as shown in Table 2, reflecting common issues identified in prior research on academic research processes.

Table 2. *Identified Challenges in the Undergraduate Research Process*

Stage	Identified Challenges
1. Research Preliminaries	Clarity and Understanding of Procedures; Title and Topic Selection; Group Dynamics and Collaboration; Research Framework and Literature Review; Resource Constraints
2. Research Proposal	Clarity and Structure of Research Proposal; Multiple Perspectives and Critiques; Time Management and Pressure; Revision and Framework Adjustments; Literature Review Challenges; Group Dynamics and Collaboration; Disagreement on Research Format; Topic Selection; Outdated Templates
3. Research Proposal Defense	Language and Communication Proficiency; Constraints in Time and Resources; Group Dynamics and Dependency; Nervousness and Performance Anxiety
4. Approval of Request Letters	Time Constraints; Grammar and Language Proficiency Challenges; Revision and Follow-up Requirements; Format and Template Errors; Revision Fatigue from Multiple Edits
5. Full Research Paper	Repeated Revisions and Editing Burden; Grammatical Errors and Inconsistencies; Long Critique Times from English Critics
6. Research Final Defense	Time Constraints and Preparation Burden; Revision and Alignment Issues; Nervousness and Overthinking; Technical Errors in Presentation; Multiple Recommendations and Re-Defenses
7. Research Output	Revising and Incorporating Feedback; Financial Constraints
8. Research Publication and Presentation	Financial Constraints; Time Management; Addressing Reviewer Comments; Transportation Issues

In the Research Preliminaries stage, students reported difficulties with clarity and understanding of procedures, title and topic selection, group dynamics, and resource constraints. These findings align with previous studies emphasizing the need for clear

guidelines and effective mentorship in the initial stages of research to prevent confusion and inefficiency (Gruber et al., 2020). Resource constraints further exacerbate these issues, as noted by Çamalan (2023), highlighting the importance of adequate resources for successful research outcomes.

During the Research Proposal phase, challenges such as clarity and structure of proposals, time management, and multiple perspectives emerged prominently. This is consistent with earlier research by Rastri et al. (2023), which found that the complexity of proposal development often leads to stress and confusion among students. Additionally, issues with outdated templates and disagreement on research formats underscore the need for updated, standardized materials, echoing recommendations from previous literature (Rosa, 2023).

The Research Proposal Defense stage was marked by language proficiency issues, time and resource constraints, and performance anxiety. These findings support earlier research by Anuyahong (2018), who reported that communication skills and anxiety are critical factors affecting students' performance during defenses. The dependence on group dynamics also highlights the importance of teamwork and collaborative skills (Santos, 2021).

For the Approval of Request Letters, students faced challenges with time constraints, grammar, and language proficiency, and revision fatigue. Similar issues were reported by Davis et al. (2022), who emphasized the need for streamlined administrative processes and better language support services to alleviate these burdens.

In completing the Full Research Paper, the burden of repeated revisions, grammatical errors, and lengthy critique times from English critics were major concerns. These challenges are consistent with findings by McKinley & Rose (2018), who pointed out that extensive revisions and language barriers often impede the timely completion of research papers.

The Research Final Defense stage presented issues with time constraints, revision alignment, and technical errors, alongside nervousness and overthinking. These challenges mirror those identified by Seals (2022), who stressed the need for comprehensive preparation and technical support to enhance students' confidence and presentation quality.

For the Research Output, revising and incorporating feedback, along with financial constraints, were significant hurdles. Previous studies, such as those by Cele et al. (2014), have also highlighted the financial challenges faced by students in producing final research outputs, underscoring the need for institutional support.

Finally, in the Research Publication and Presentation phase, financial constraints, time management, and transportation issues were prevalent. These issues align with earlier research by Garwe (2015), who noted that logistical and financial barriers often hinder students' ability to disseminate their research effectively.

Overall, the challenges identified in this study corroborate existing literature on the difficulties faced by undergraduate researchers. Addressing these challenges through targeted interventions and support mechanisms, as suggested by the respondents, can significantly enhance the research process and outcomes for students at Holy Cross College and similar institutions.

Suggestions for Improving the Undergraduate Research Process

To address the challenges encountered, respondents provided several suggestions for improving the undergraduate research process. These suggestions, consolidated into emerging themes as shown in Table 3, resonate with findings from previous research, highlighting their relevance and potential effectiveness.

Table 3. Identified Suggestions for Improvement in the Undergraduate Research Process

Stage	Identified Suggestions for Improvement
1. Research Preliminaries	Discussion of the Research Process; Sufficient Preparation Time; Literature Review and Resource Exploration; Clarity in Title Selection; Adviser Support
2. Research Proposal	Timely Feedback; Template Accuracy; Sufficient Preparation Time; Literature Review and Resource Exploration
3. Research Proposal Defense	Sufficient Preparation Time; Group Dynamics; Timely feedback; Communication of Defense Mechanics
4. Approval of Request Letters	Letter Template Accuracy; Sufficient Preparation Time
5. Full Research Paper	Sufficient Preparation Time; Develop Writing Process Outline
6. Research Final Defense	Limit Presentation Time
7. Research Output	Improved Communication Channels
8. Research Publication and Presentation	Financial Support; Tools and Strategies for Managing Research Presentation

In the Research Preliminaries stage, recommendations such as discussing the research process, providing sufficient preparation time, facilitating literature review and resource exploration, ensuring clarity in title selection, and offering adviser support align with prior studies. Jeyaraj (2018) emphasized the importance of clear guidance and adequate preparation time in enhancing students' understanding and confidence during the initial stages of research. Additionally, the need for adviser support echoes the findings of Li (2019), who identified mentorship as a critical factor in navigating

early research challenges.

For the Research Proposal phase, suggestions for timely feedback, template accuracy, sufficient preparation time, and enhanced literature review and resource exploration are well-supported by existing literature. Mattson (2017) stressed that timely and structured feedback is crucial in helping students develop well-structured proposals. The emphasis on template accuracy addresses the issue of outdated and inconsistent formats, a problem highlighted by Rosa (2023).

The Research Proposal Defense stage recommendations—sufficient preparation time, group dynamics improvement, timely feedback, and clear communication of defense mechanics—reflect common themes in academic research. Lajom et al. (2023) noted that preparation time and clear communication significantly reduce performance anxiety and improve defense outcomes. Akindele (2012) also underscored the importance of effective group dynamics in collaborative research efforts.

For the Approval of Request Letters stage, focusing on letter template accuracy and sufficient preparation time addresses administrative challenges. Streamlining administrative processes and providing clear templates can reduce the time and effort required for approvals, improving overall efficiency (Tantua, 2022).

In the Full Research Paper stage, the recommendation for sufficient preparation time and developing a writing process outline aligns with Gopee and Deane (2013), who emphasized structured writing support to help students manage the demands of academic writing. Providing a clear outline and timeline for the writing process can reduce the burden of revisions and improve the quality of the final paper.

For the Research Final Defense, limiting presentation time addresses the issue of time constraints and preparation burdens. Krysik (2018) highlighted that concise and focused presentations are more effective and less stressful for students, improving their performance during defenses.

The suggestion for improved communication channels in the Research Output stage aims to facilitate the incorporation of feedback, a critical step identified by Armengol-Asparó et al. (2022). Efficient communication between students, advisers, and evaluators can streamline the revision process and ensure the timely completion of research outputs.

Finally, in the Research Publication and Presentation phase, the need for financial support and tools for managing research presentations is well-documented. Garwe (2015) found that financial constraints often limit students' ability to publish and present their work. Providing financial support and practical tools can significantly enhance students' opportunities for disseminating their research.

Overall, the suggestions for improvement are well-founded in previous research and offer a practical roadmap for enhancing the undergraduate research process at Holy

Cross College. By addressing identified challenges with targeted interventions, these recommendations have the potential to improve the quality and efficiency of student research through business process reengineering, ultimately leading to better academic outcomes.

Reengineering the Undergraduate Research Process

The findings from the identified challenges and suggestions for improvement served as a basis for the BPR approach to be applied in the undergraduate research process. Reengineering each stage of the undergraduate research process focused on improving efficiency, effectiveness, and student satisfaction.

Table 4. BPR Approach for Improving the Undergraduate Research Process

Stage	Current Process	Reengineered Process
1. Research Preliminaries	Students prepare and submit preliminary research to faculty for approval.	<p>Clarity and Training: Implement workshops and orientation sessions at the beginning of the research preliminaries stage to discuss the entire research process, clarify procedures, and provide guidance on title and topic selection.</p> <p>Resource Accessibility: Develop an online repository with literature resources and a clear research framework template accessible to all students.</p> <p>Adviser Allocation: Assign dedicated research advisers early in the process to provide consistent support and address group dynamics and collaboration challenges.</p>
2. Research Proposal	Approved preliminaries lead to the preparation of a formal proposal with the help of the advisory panel.	<p>Feedback Mechanism: Establish a structured timeline for timely feedback from advisers and peers to ensure continuous improvement and timely adjustments.</p> <p>Template Standardization: Update and standardize research proposal templates to avoid outdated formats and discrepancies.</p> <p>Preparation Time: Allocate sufficient preparation time and schedule regular check-ins to monitor progress and address time management issues.</p> <p>Resource Support: Enhance access to literature review resources and provide workshops on effective literature exploration techniques.</p>

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| 3. Research Proposal Defense | Complete proposals are recommended for defense and presented before the defense panel. | <p>Preparation and Training: Offer mock defense sessions and communication skills workshops to reduce nervousness and improve language proficiency.</p> <p>Clear Defense Guidelines: Develop and communicate detailed guidelines and mechanics for the defense process, ensuring students understand expectations.</p> |
| 4. Approval of Request Letters | Letters are submitted for approval, with multiple revisions often required. | <p>Template Accuracy: Create accurate, pre-approved letter templates to reduce errors and revision fatigue.</p> <p>Streamlined Approval Process: Implement an online submission and tracking system to streamline the approval process, allowing for easier follow-ups and status checks.</p> |
| 5. Full Research Paper | Completion of research paper after obtaining ethics approval. | <p>Writing Support: Develop a comprehensive writing process outline and provide ongoing writing workshops and one-on-one support sessions.</p> <p>Revision Management: Use collaborative tools for tracking revisions and feedback to minimize the burden of repeated editing.</p> <p>Grammar Assistance: Provide access to language and grammar support services to reduce inconsistencies and errors.</p> |
| 6. Research Final Defense | Complete research papers are recommended for final defense and submitted to panelists. | <p>Presentation Training: Conduct presentation skills workshops and offer tools to help students prepare concise and effective presentations.</p> <p>Time Management: Limit presentation time to ensure clarity and reduce preparation burden.</p> <p>Technical Support: Provide technical assistance and resources to avoid errors during presentations.</p> |
| 7. Research Output | The final research output is checked, approved, and reproduced. | <p>Communication Channels: Establish efficient communication channels between students, advisers, and faculty to ensure timely feedback and approvals.</p> |

8. Research Publication and Presentation	Best papers are selected for publication and presentation.	Financial Support: Allocate funds and resources to support students in publishing and presenting their research. Publication Assistance: Assist students in navigating the publication process, including formatting and submission to relevant journals.
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Conclusions and Recommendations

The evaluation of the undergraduate research process at Holy Cross College provides valuable insights into advancing the field of undergraduate research management and support. This study contributes to the field by systematically assessing student perceptions across multiple stages of the research process, from preliminaries to publication and presentation. The high ratings, particularly in stages like Research Final Defense, underscore effective institutional support and structured processes that validate student research efforts, thus reinforcing existing best practices in undergraduate research pedagogy.

By identifying persistent challenges such as time constraints, collaboration dynamics, and resource limitations, the findings substantiate the need for targeted interventions to enhance the undergraduate research experience. The recommendations for improvement, including better preparation time, clearer communication channels, and institutional support for publication, offer actionable strategies to mitigate these challenges. Implementing these suggestions not only addresses immediate undergraduate researcher needs but also contributes to the ongoing discourse on optimizing research environments and outcomes in the higher education sector.

Looking forward, future studies could explore the longitudinal impact of implemented improvements on student research outcomes and institutional research culture. Further investigation into the effectiveness of digital tools and technological solutions in streamlining research processes could also yield innovative approaches to enhance student engagement and scholarly productivity. Additionally, comparative studies across diverse institutional contexts and disciplines would provide insights into the generalizability of findings and the adaptation of best practices to different educational settings.

In conclusion, this study at Holy Cross College advances the field by offering empirical evidence and practical recommendations to enhance undergraduate research management. By addressing identified challenges and proposing systematic improvements, it contributes to the present state of knowledge in undergraduate research pedagogy and sets a foundation for future studies to build upon, thereby fostering continuous improvement in research education and student success.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were integral to the research design and implementation. Participants were provided with informed consent detailing the purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature of their participation. Confidentiality measures were strictly observed to protect participants' identities and ensure the anonymity of their responses. By adhering to these guidelines, the study aimed to respect the rights and well-being of participants while gathering valuable data to improve the undergraduate research process at Holy Cross College, Sta. Rosa, N.E.

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